

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BEZABEH****FIRST NAME: MINILIK****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author X did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author X did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024) and the general understanding of plagiarism mentioned in the ACA-401D coursepack, which best describes plagiarism?
 - Using another person's ideas and crediting them fully.
 - Creating entirely new content without referencing any external sources.
 - Using someone else's work or ideas without giving them proper credit.¹**
 - Sharing your own previously written work with different audiences.
2. Which of the following statements best summarizes the importance of adhering to a formal writing style in academic essays, discussed by Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024)?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

- It allows for the use of slang and colloquial expressions to engage readers.
 - It ensures consistency and professionalism, improving readability and adherence to academic norms.²**
 - It permits flexibility in punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary usage.
 - It emphasizes using informal language to make the content more relatable.
3. What is the significance of having a well-defined research problem in a study, as described in the Turabian Rule of style?
- It allows for a broad investigation of many topics simultaneously.
 - It encourages using ambiguous and varied problem statements to explore diverse outcomes.
 - It focuses on solving already addressed issues to reinforce previous findings.
 - It provides a clear direction and purpose, highlighting gaps in knowledge that the study aims to address.³**
4. What distinguishes a conceptual research problem from a practical one, as outlined in the Turabian Rule of Style?
- A conceptual research problem addresses a lack of understanding or knowledge to advance theoretical frameworks, while a practical research problem deals with issues requiring concrete solutions and societal impact.⁴**

² Ibid., 41.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

⁴ Ibid., 29.

- A conceptual research problem focuses on tangible solutions with direct societal benefits, while a practical research problem seeks to refine theoretical frameworks.
 - Both types of problems aim to provide theoretical insights without real-world applications.
 - A conceptual research problem only involves subjective issues without influencing theoretical understanding.
5. How do contemporary readers generally perceive arguments based on warrants compared to those based on evidence, as the Turabian Rule of Style explains?
- Readers find arguments based on warrants to be more trustworthy and credible than those based on evidence.
 - Readers are indifferent to the type of argument presented as long as the claims are plausible.
 - Readers only trust arguments that combine both warrants and emotional appeals.
 - Readers typically prefer arguments based on evidence because they provide solid support for claims, while arguments based solely on warrants are viewed as less reliable.⁵**
6. According to the Turabian Rule of Style, what guidelines must be followed for accurate quoting in academic work?
- All sources used in a paper should only be listed once at the end, regardless of their citation format.

⁵ Ibid., 66.

- Quotations can be paraphrased without any need for documentation if the original source is acknowledged in the bibliography.
- Direct quotations must be replicated verbatim, with brief quotes integrated into the text and longer ones formatted as block quotes, and small modifications are allowed for context.⁶**
- Quotations do not need to be exact as long as the general idea is conveyed; citation style can be chosen freely.

7. What key characteristics and practices are essential for conducting qualitative dissertation research, according to Sampson (2017)?

- A researcher should focus solely on quantitative data, as qualitative analysis lacks rigor and credibility.
- Qualitative research is a static process that does not require collaboration with advisors, and it emphasizes personal biases over empirical evidence.
- Conducting qualitative dissertation research requires critical thinking, and collaboration with academic peers and involves creating multiple documents with an understanding of how qualitative and quantitative methodologies can be integrated while recognizing inherent biases.⁷**
- A researcher must avoid any form of documentation regarding potential biases to ensure the research appears objective.

⁶ Ibid., 371.

⁷ James P. Sampson. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1.

8. What essential components should be included in the methodology section of a research study, as described by Bloomberg and Volpe (2019)?
- A detailed account of the researcher's personal opinions and theoretical perspectives without empirical support.
 - A summary of the study's design and processes, covering the research setting, demographics, sample, and detailed descriptions of data collection and analytical methods.⁸**
 - An overview of unrelated literature and previous studies that do not connect to the current research design.
 - The focus is solely on qualitative methods, excluding quantitative data collection and analysis.
9. What capitalization rules does the European Commission outline regarding nouns and institutional names, and what considerations are advised for using all capitals?
- Proper nouns must be capitalized, while common nouns remain lowercase; specific institutional names from foreign languages should retain their original capitalization, and the use of all capitals should be reserved for conveying significant importance, avoiding block capitals for entire sentences.⁹**
 - Only common nouns need to be capitalized when referring to groups of institutions, while permanent EU bodies and official roles remain lowercase in all formats.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation* (Los Angeles: Columbia University, 2017), 80.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide* (European Commission, 2021), 23.

- All nouns, including common nouns, should always start with a capital letter, and the excessive use of all capitals is encouraged for emphasis.
- Translating institutional names into English removes the need to follow capitalization rules, allowing for flexibility based on personal preference.

10. According to the European Commission, what are the rules for incorporating foreign words and phrases into English texts, and what precautions should be taken?

- All foreign words and phrases must be placed in quotation marks, regardless of their usage in modern English, and common Latin expressions do not require italics.
- Italicization is only required for foreign words commonly understood in English; all other foreign words should be kept in standard Roman type without any accents.
- There are no specific guidelines regarding using foreign words in English texts, so writers can use any format they prefer.
- Foreign words and phrases are typically italicized with the correct accents, but no quotation marks and it is essential to avoid italics for names of people, institutions, and places; caution is advised to prevent misuse of assimilated terms.¹⁰**

¹⁰ Ibid., 48.

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